

Federated governance for Europe’s network of trusted research environments

“The examples of CERN and the European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC) showcase the importance of coordination when developing large R&I infrastructure projects.”

– The Draghi Report¹ (Part A, p29)

Summary

The EOSC-ENTRUST project² builds on real-world needs and best practices to realise a coordinated network of interoperable trusted research environments (TREs), data providers and essential research services. The recommendations in our first policy brief³ highlighted the increasing importance of TREs as enablers of data-driven research and the need for technical interoperability between them.

This brief extends these ideas, highlighting the federation and governance approaches needed to create a trustworthy research infrastructure on top of this interoperable network of TREs.

Large-scale scientific federations have been a European mainstay for decades, from over 30 European Research Infrastructure Consortia⁴ to transnational examples such as CERN and EMBL. A federation provides its community with an authoritative voice and often a set of shared or common services, supporting standards, collaboration and trust. Most scientific federations to date have arisen in “scientific verticals”, serving communities of particular disciplines.

The concept of federation across “horizontal capabilities” is newer but is a compelling model for enabling national and transnational research with sensitive data, aligning as it does with the complex sets of specialisations needed to operate a TRE.

Highlighting the need for coordination at scale in the domain of health data, for example, the Draghi Report¹ recommends (Part A, p35) “... EU-level support for national investments which facilitate access to and sharing of electronic health records” to enable EU nations to realise the full research benefits offered by the European Health Data Space (EHDS)⁵.

Smaller-scale examples of TRE federations have emerged recently in Switzerland⁶, in Norway⁷ and in Scotland⁸, and EOSC-ENTRUST has collected strong evidence in favour of a federated approach throughout its first year, from its driving use cases⁹ to its overall network architecture¹⁰.

Europe can seize the opportunities presented by TREs to position itself at the forefront of data-driven research. Accordingly, we make four new recommendations for decision-makers in this space.

“ Recommendations

1. Adopt a federated approach and plan for a federation-of-federations.
2. Design governance models alongside infrastructure, not afterwards.
3. Invest in accreditation, including both training and assessment, to create trust.
4. Consider co-locating major data and compute infrastructure investments.

About EOSC-ENTRUST and TREs

EOSC-ENTRUST’s vision is a network of interoperable, nationally governed trusted research environments (TREs) capable of supporting large-scale European research and analysis efforts on sensitive and restricted data.

TREs are secure computing environments designed to handle sensitive data safely, digital reference libraries where researchers “visit” and analyse data in controlled environments, but cannot take the data away; only approved summaries may ever be exported. TREs come in various shapes and sizes, including “secure processing environments”, “secure data environments” and “data safe havens”, but their general purpose is to enable researchers to access sensitive datasets whilst ensuring privacy is maintained.

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Recommendation 1

Adopt a federated approach

As the “data visiting” model replaces the “data download” model and the number of TREs rises, both existing and new TREs must adopt a “federation-first” approach. A federation, where partners come together with a shared purpose and common set of rules, provides a strong foundation for trust, and mutual trust sits at the heart of a network of TREs. TREs will increasingly become not only secure processing environments but also libraries of curated, research-ready sensitive data, and while

technical interoperability is essential, more important still is mutual trust.

Although federations form more easily among organisations in similar sectors or disciplines, the true power of sensitive data research comes from linking data cross-sector. Therefore, to reach their potential impact, TREs must plan to operate not only in one federation but in many – an approach sometimes called a “federation-of-federations”.

Recommendation 2

Design governance alongside infrastructure

Clear, inclusive and widely accepted governance is essential to the success of a federation-of-federations approach. The designs of individual TREs are often heavily influenced by the information governance needs of their data-provider stakeholders. Integrating multiple governance perspectives into interoperating federation structures is complex and must be prioritised and planned from the outset.

Policy and funding incentives at the European and national level should strongly encourage the developers and builders of TRE services to work together not only on technical interoperability but also on joint governance. Disparate groups such as infrastructure designers, data authorities and legal experts should be incentivised to work as a single team to realise interoperable federations of TREs.

Governance depends on multiple strands which must fit together and be developed together.

These include:

- Harmonised governance of inter-regional and international data access within a given sector or discipline. The EHDS legislation is an exemplar driver of harmonised governance in the secondary use of health data for research.
- Shared metadata standards to enable cross-disciplinary data linkage.
- Governance of the technical standards required to achieve federation interoperability, including agreements on ongoing editorial and change processes.
- Standard operating procedures across and between federations, including standard registry and trust services, network cybersecurity and incident response.

Recommendation 3

Invest in accreditation

Federations are built on trust. Trust can arise naturally between two or three parties as they work together over a period of time. However, this approach can break down as the number of parties increases. Adopting common operational and security standards can support trust at scale, but must be underpinned by clear and credible accreditation frameworks.

Common standards and independent assessment provide the necessary levels of

assurance. Existing international standards such as ISO/IEC 27001 on information security management are not sufficient to meet the unique demands of TRE operations such as disclosure control. New accreditation regimes for TRE operation are necessary to build and sustain trust within and between federations, such as the regime currently being developed for the EHDS. However, they require real investment in auditing and accreditation capacity.

Recommendation 4

Consider co-locating compute and data

Realising the benefits to public policy offered by artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) requires two things: large, high-quality datasets; and powerful computers. In the area of sensitive personal data, such large datasets—genetic data in biobanks, for example, or medical imaging collections—are typically few in number and very often nationally curated. To enable research using AI and ML techniques on such data resources requires that research be carried out in a TRE. Currently, few TREs have the necessary compute power to make this feasible, and current investments in large-scale AI factories mean that these big systems can be sited at a distance from the data of interest. Moving sensitive data around the Internet at scale whilst maintaining appropriate governance and security postures is a significant challenge.

One approach to mitigating this challenge would be to co-locate new AI compute resources alongside the major data repositories relevant for a given sector or community, and to design them as TREs instead of as “classic” high-performance computing systems. For example, locating a major new compute resource for ML using medical images alongside an existing regional or national medical image data archive will make it far easier to combine the two into a single TRE. This will enable significantly more powerful and useful AI models to be researched and developed whilst reducing the risks and delays of moving large, sensitive datasets across the Internet. This co-location should be a significant factor in the commissioning of new compute investments.

Policy Implications

“Research and innovation (R&I) are the main drivers of productivity and people’s well-being”.¹¹

Research and innovation are driven ever more by data. Providing researchers with access to sensitive data—about citizens, about migrants, about intellectual property—can unlock tremendous insight, but requires investment in an interoperable network of trusted research environments with the capabilities to support modern research methods involving machine learning and artificial intelligence. To make such a trans-European network trustworthy, and to ensure data access is controlled and managed safely and ethically, requires an approach that is transparent, federated and governed appropriately.

EOSC-ENTRUST is pioneering these approaches for Europe. We call on policymakers and funders to embrace the federation model for trusted research and to support it through investment, advocacy and public engagement.

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Acknowledgement

EOSC-ENTRUST project receives funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101131056.

**Funded by
the European Union**

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